

ADHESIVE-BONDING ASSEMBLY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

JEANDRAU Jean-Pierre
CEntre Technique des Industries Mécaniques
10, rue Barrouin
42029 SAINT-ETIENNE Cedex 1 (France)
Tel : (33) 77 43 39 76
Fax : (33) 77 43 39 99

ABSTRACT

Adhesive-bonding is a widely used technology for assembling composite materials together or on other materials (plastic or metallic) because it offers many main benefits :

- universality,
- doesn't weaken the structure,
- noises and vibrations damping,
- stiffnesses and fatigue behaviour of structures improved,
- light and esthetic structures,
- watertightness assured,
- costs reductions...

These advantages (and also the limitations) will be illustrated on industrial applications.

However, each step involved during the realization of a bonded assembly must be pragmatically and scientifically approached if reliable and durable structures are to be obtained.

In this paper, the present state of knowledge in the following areas is resumed :

- surface pretreatments,
- adhesive selection,
- analysis and design,
- quality-control,

For each of these areas, the means and tools developed by CETIM to help users are also reviewed (softwares, test equipments, collective studies, publications, training courses...).

Keywords : Adhesive-bonding ; composite materials, benefits, limits, surface preparations, adhesive selection, analysis and design, quality-control.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of their high costs, their complex production process and their mechanical behaviour not well known, advanced composite materials (carbone/epoxyde, glass/epoxyde, Kevlar/epoxyde) have been essentially used in industries of high technological level (aerospace, competitive sports...) during the ten last years.

Since less expensive and easier producible materials have appeared on the market (glass/polyester, reinforced thermoplastics...), every industrial areas use more and more composite materials (automotive industry, sports-leisure, armament, transports, white goods...). Besides these materials are specific with regard to their production process and their mechanical behaviour, they must be joined together or with other metallic or plastic materials. Among the joining technologies known (screwing, mechanical fastening, adhesive-bonding...) the last mentioned is certainly the most universal and attractive one.

2. WHY ADHESIVE-BONDING ? BENEFITS AND LIMITS

Among the benefits of the adhesive-bonding technology against the other possible joining techniques for these materials, we can mention :

- the universality : All the materials can be bonded (more or less easily) together and on other materials, providing precautions are made with regard to the requirements of the application ;
- the respect of the integrity of the materials and structures : adhesive-bonding occurs at room or moderate temperatures ($\leq 200^{\circ}\text{C}$) so that the structural properties of metals and alloys won't be thermally affected by the curing process of the adhesive ; on the other hand, adhesive bonding doesn't imply to drill holes in the structures (as it is made in the case of the screwing method) so that structures aren't weakened by reductions of the working sections or by ruptures of fibres (very negative effect in composite structures) ;
- the continuity of the joint : which gives to adhesively-bonded structures stiffnesses and fatigue performances higher than those obtained on other joining methods ;
- noises and vibrations damping thanks to the presence of a continuous film of polymer ;
- the watertightness is obtained without any other supplementary procedure (sealants...) ;
- the structures are lighter (because of their integrity kept and their higher stiffnesses) ;
- adhesively-bonded structures are esthetic (no overthicknesses, no holes, aerodynamism not perturbed...).

All these advantages mentioned above can lead to significant cost reductions in many cases. These benefits will be illustrated and detailed on industrial case-studies presented during this conference.

Among the limits with regard to this joining technology, we can mention :

- the temperature resistance, which, above 250°C , requires using specific adhesives difficult to make use of ;
- bonded structures can't be dismantled ;
- the need to realize sometimes complex surface pretreatments in order to "bond" some materials ;
- the lack of experience and knowledge for predicting the durability of bonded structures (fatigue, creep, humid aging...) ;
- the lack of reliable non-destructive-techniques.

3. SURFACE PRETREATMENTS BEFORE BONDING

To obtain a structural adhesively-bonded joint, the first concern of the designer will be the avoidance of interfacial failures (see figure 1). For that, he has to optimize the surface pretreatment of the adherends. This parameter is of prime importance in order to obtain reliable and durable adhesively-bonded joints.

Figure 1 - Different modes of failure in an adhesively-bonded joint.

Surface preparations of composite materials are easier than those used for metallic or thermoplastic materials. The nature of the resin in the composite will govern the choice of the surface pretreatment :

- if it is a thermosetting resin (epoxyde, polyester, phenolic, polyurethane...) a mechanical abrasion will be enough (sanding, sand-blasting, scotch-brite...) to eliminate released agents on the surface, followed by a degreasing step (methyl-ethyl-ketone is widely used) ; this pretreatment can be avoided if a peel-ply has been used to produce the composite material ;
- if it is a thermoplastic resin (polyethylene, polypropylene, fluorinated resins, poly vinyl chloride..., polyamides...) it will be necessary to realize specific surface pretreatments in order to increase the surface tensions of these materials (chemical treatments, flame treatment, "corona" or "plasma" treatments, UV irradiations, primers...).

For metallic alloys, the surface preparation consists in removing layers of pollutants (greases, lubricants...) by degreasing with organic solvents or alkaline cleaning agents and then in eliminating the initial oxide layer (not suitable for adhesive bonding) by a mechanical abrasion (sandblasting,...) or a chemical etching (basic or acid). In order to obtain a good durability in hostile environments (hot/wet, water, marine environment, chemical products...), the metallic pieces are chemically treated, this treatment being purposed to dissolve the initial oxide layer and to replace it by a new one by controlling its formation (thickness, structure, composition) by the chemical parameters of the batches (composition, time, temperature, rinsing conditions...), this new oxide layer being stable and suitable for adhesive bonding (ex : sulfochromic etching, chromic or phosphoric acid anodisations for aluminium alloys).

As part of the realization of a database on adhesive-bonding technology, CETIM has developed a software "CETIM-PRESUR" which enables to select the appropriate surface preparations according to the materials to be bonded and to the requirements of the application (environment, life-time and mechanical loadings..).

This software, implemented on IBM/PC microcomputers, enables the interrogation of a file containing about 500 different surface pretreatments (description, directions for use, products, suppliers) concerning more than 100 materials (metallics and alloys, composites, plastics, rubbers, glass, ceramics...).

4. ADHESIVE SELECTION - SELECTION CRITERIA

The correct choice of an adhesive for a specific application is very complex because of the important number of different adhesives found on the market and because of the diversity of applications. Though, it is necessary to analyse precisely the requirements of the joint in order to deduce the appropriate selection criteria and determine the family (or the references) of adhesives suitable. Among these selection criteria (technical but also economical) we'll mention :

- the chemical compatibility of the adhesive with the adherends (if possible, it will be interesting to use an adhesive of the same chemical nature than the resin of the composite ; but there are no well known incompatibilities with composites, except with modified-acrylic or anaerobic adhesives in certain conditions) ;
- the temperature range (service and storage conditions) ;
- the environment of the joint (oils, fuel, humidity, water, marine conditions..) ;
- the mechanical loadings (static, dynamic) with their directions and levels ;
- the design of the joints (plan or cylindrical joints, gap-filling) ;
- the place where the joint is made (laboratory, workshop, building site...) ;
- the curing process (room temperature, elevated temperature, pressure.) ;
- the production (mass-production, rates...).

Among the adhesives used for bonding composite materials together or on other materials we can mention :

- epoxyde adhesives (films, pastes or liquids), one-part or two-parts for all structural applications,
- polyurethane adhesives (two-parts) for semi-structural bonded joints of large areas and (or) for bonding materials with different thermal expansion coefficients,
- modified acrylic adhesives (providing that their chemical compatibility with the resins of the composites has been tested) for structural applications,
- thermally stable adhesives (polyimides, polybenzimidazoles...) for applications requiring high service temperatures (300-500°C), but with complex curing processes,
- cyanoacrylates for bonding small and smooth pieces, not subjected to impact loading and (or) humidity,
- hot-melts and acrylic tapes for many semi-structural applications.

The software "CETIM-LORA" implemented on IBM/PC microcomputers has been developed to enable users to select one or several adhesives answering to precise requirements according to a multicriteria selection procedure. The criteria used are those mentioned above. The correspondant file contains technical data concerning about 1000 adhesives (information on suppliers, physical and chemical characteristics, curing process, thermal and mechanical characteristics).

5. ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF ADHESIVELY BONDED-JOINTS

When the surface preparations and the adhesive have been correctly selected according to the requirements, it isn't enough to ensure the reliability of the bonded-joint.

In fact, the designer has to design and dimension correctly the joint.

The design will be specific to adhesively-bonded joints :

- the tensile strength of an adhesive is 10 to 100 times lower than those of materials to be joined ; so it is necessary to have large areas in contact (overlapping for plan joints, and for cylindrical or tubular joints) in order to transmit acceptable loads ;
- avoid local loadings of the adhesive (peel or cleavage stresses), but prefer to load the joint in tension or shear ;
- for composite materials with long fibers, take care of the fibers orientation at the interface adhesive/adherend with regard to the load direction axis (the tensile-shear strength of unidirectionnel kevlar/epoxy and carbone/epoxy composites bonded with epoxy adhesives can be 30% to 3 times higher when the fibers in contact with the adhesive layer are parallel to the tensile axis than those obtained when these fibers are perpendicular to the tensile axis) [1].

For dimensionning adhesively-bonded joints, empirical methods have been widely used until to these last years.

The software "CETIM-CA-DI-AC", implemented on IBM/PC microcomputers, enables to analyse the mechanical behaviour of bonded joints of simple configurations such as :

- single-lap joints loaded in tension [2, 3],
- double-lap joints loaded in tension or (and) in shear [4],
- tubular-lap joints loaded in tension [5] and in torsion [6]

This software is based on published analytical methods [2 - 6], the principal assumptions made are the linear elastic or the elastoplastic behaviour of the adhesive.

According to the hypothesis made (elastic or elastoplastic analyses) and the strength criterion used (VON-MISES stress for elastic analysis, and maximum shear-strain for elastoplastic analysis), we can determine the load bearable by the joint ("reversibility" limit of the joint, or failure strength of the joint [7]).

Because of their easy implementation and low-cost exploitation (fast calculations), these analytical methods can be used as a design tool in the software CETIM-CA.DI.AC in order to see the influence of parameters such as : the overlap length, the adherends and adhesive mechanical characteristics and their thicknesses....

For more complex configurations, the CA.ST.OR finite element software developed at CETIM can be used.

In order to run these softwares described above (CA.DI.AC and CA.ST.OR), the designer needs some mechanical characteristics (such as elastic moduli, stresses and strains at failure..) not currently found in the technical data sheets given by adhesive suppliers. These mechanical properties can't be determined with classical standard test methods (tension-shear NF T 76-107, peel NF T 76-112..) because of the state of stress non uniaxial and non uniform in these specimens.

In order to determine these characteristics, CETIM uses a test methodology [8, 9, 10] based on tensile and compressive tests on the bulk adhesive, and on shear tests on thick-adherend-shear specimens (see figure 2).

More than 20 adhesives have been already tested at CETIM over a wide range of temperatures and environmental conditions.

The thick-adherend-shear specimen is being used at CETIM for creep and fatigue purposes.

These test methods should enable the adhesive manufacturers to give mechanical characteristics of structural adhesives of interest for the engineers in order to dimension and predict the durability of bonded structures submitted to creep and fatigue.

6. QUALITY-CONTROL OF ADHESIVELY-BONDED JOINTS

According to the nature of the bonded joint (use, cost, reliability and durability to be obtained..) the quality control procedure used will be less or more complex. The different steps concern

- The surface preparation of adherends control :
 - roughness measurement,
 - wetting ability measurement (spreading of a drop of water, contact angle measurements, surface tensions measurements...),
 - surface structure and topography observations (optical or electron-scanning or electron-transmission microscopies),
 - qualitative or quantitative chemical analyses of outside layers (AUGER or XES spectroscopy, ESCA, SIMS...),
 - destructive tests on bonded-joints (peel test according to NF T 76-112, wedge-test according to NF T 76-114 or 3 points flexure test according to NF T 76-143..) ;
- The control of the adhesive before curing (reception and storage controls) ;
 - aspect,
 - viscosity,
 - infrared spectrum,
 - reactivity (differential scanning calorimetry),
 - dry extract and ash content...;
- The control of the cured adhesive :
 - curing ratio, glass-transition temperature (DSC),
 - destructive tests on bonded joints (tensile-shear according to NF T 76-107...);
- The final non-destructive testing of the bonded assembly :
 - to control the presence of the adhesive (detection of bubbles, voids, porosities...) by ultrasonic methods or electromagnetic radiations methods (infrared thermography, X-ray radiography, holographic interferometry...) ;
 - to control the cohesion of the adhesive layer (incorrect curing process, bad ratio and mixing conditions for two-parts adhesives; using fine analysis of ultrasonic signals or methods based on the sonic resonance (FOKKER-BOND-TESTER or BONDASCOPE 2100...) ,

- to control the quality of the adhesion (bad surface preparation, contamination of the surfaces...) : for this control, no reliable industrial method is available now and fundamental research has to be carried out in order to solve this problem.

Its equipments enable CETIM to carry out most of the quality control procedures mentioned above according to industrial needs.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The adhesive-bonding department of CETIM, located at SAINT-ETIENNE has carried out collective studies, in collaboration with other laboratories as part of national programmes (GIS-Collage, DRET...) or european programmes (BRITE, EUREKA) which have led to :

- the development of an "adhesive-data bank" enabling the centralisation of technical data on most of the technical adhesives available on the French and European markets and on surface-pretreatments of adherends (metals and alloys, plastics, composites...) and softwares enabling the selection of appropriate solutions for adhesive bonding called " CETIM-PRESUR" and "CETIM-LORA" ;
- the development of a software for the design and stress-analysis of adhesively bonded joints for structural applications "CETIM-CA.DI.AC" ;
- the development of standardized test methods enabling the determination of the mechanical characteristics of structural adhesives of interest for the designers (in order to dimension bonded structures) ;
- the elaboration of generic models enabling the prediction of the durability of a bonded-joint submitted to severe environment conditions (humidity, heat...) and to long-term mechanical loadings (creep, fatigue).

Thanks to its testing equipments, CETIM is able to apply most of the quality control procedures for adhesive-bonding technology.

The adhesive-bonding department of CETIM offers many services to industrials enabling them to use the adhesive-bonding technology correctly :

- publications,
- direct technical assistance
- course-training
- participation to the French and European standardization work....

REFERENCES

- [1] JEANDRAU, J.P., PAULIARD, R., "*Collage des matériaux composites*" Rapport ETCA N° 82R051, Mai 1982.
- [2] HART-SMITH, L.J., "*Adhesive bonded single lap joints*" NASA CR 112236, (1973).
- [3] WILLIAMS, J.H., "*Stresses in adhesive between dissimilar adherends*" J. of Adhesion, vol. 7, pp 97-107, (1975).
- [4] HART-SMITH, L.J., "*Adhesive bonded double lap joints*" NASA CR 112235, (1973).

- [5] LUBKIN, J.L., and REISSNER, E., "*Stress distribution and design data for adhesive lap joints between circular tubes*"
TRANS. ASME 78, pp 1213 - 1221, (1956).
- [6] ADAMS, R.D., and PEPPIATT, N.A., "*Stress analysis of adhesive bonded tubular lap joints*" - J. of Adhesion, vol. 9, pp. 1-18, (1976).
- [7] JEANDRAU, J.P., "*Calcul et dimensionnement des assemblages collés*" - 5èmes Journées d'études sur l'adhérence, Métal, Céramique, Polymères, Composites, organisées par la Société Française du Vide, Journées d'enseignement, Vol 1, Université Claude Bernard LYON I, 18-19 Juin 1990.
- [8] JEANDRAU, J.P., "*Intrinsic mechanical characterization of structural adhesives*"
Int. J. of Adhesion and Adhesives, vol. 6, n° 4, pp. 229-231, october (1986).
- [9] JEANDRAU, J.P., "*Collage structural - La fin de l'empirisme*"
CETIM-Informations, n° 100, pp. 20-25, Avril 1987.
- [10] JEANDRAU, J.P., "*Analysis and Design of adhesively bonded structural joints : New tools for engineers*" - Mechanical Behaviour of Adhesive Joints, pp. 493 - 507, PLURALIS (1987).
Proceedings of the European Mechanics Colloquium 227, held in SAINT-ETIENNE, 31 August - 2 September (1987).

a) Characterization of the bulk adhesive

b) Characterization of the adhesive in a bonded joint

Figure 2 - Test specimens for determining the intrinsic mechanical characteristics of structural adhesives